

REDUCING GENDER IMBALANCE IN THE RESEARCH COMMUNITY

MINDtheGEPs will reduce gender imbalances in European research institutions and generate data to support the development of national and European policy for gender equality in research performing organisations.

No data - no policy!

We need data to be able to develop policy to **reduce the gender gap in science**. We also need to pay attention to the organisational context. **MINDtheGEPs** (Modifying Institutions by Developing Gender Equality Plans) will collect data on the macro, meso, and micro levels, allowing us to identify the push-and-pull factors that maintain gender imbalances, and design and monitor **Gender Equality Plans** in seven European research institutions that are tailored to each specific structural and cultural context.

We work to **improve women's research career prospects**, to increase **gender balance in decision-making bodies**, and to **include gender dimensions in research content & teaching**.

We focus on **fixing the system, not the women**. We train both women and men, junior and senior, on the diffusion and causes of gender imbalances trying to break stereotypes.

We create new gender equality bodies or positions and we promote **equal representation** in main governing bodies and recruitment-promotion panels. We fight the unconditional worker model **promoting work-life balance for all**.

We promote gender equality at the **structural and cultural level** in both public and private research and innovation organisations.

MINDtheGEPs unites **10 research organisations** from **7 EU countries** in the quest to close the gender gap in research and innovation. Together, **universities, research centres, and a scientific publisher** work to ensure gender equality in academia and scientific research! Towards more open and inclusive research organisations!

www.mindthegeps.eu

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